

**MODERN METHODS OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT EDUCATION
IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES**

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Today, the rapid development of science and technology leads to great changes in all aspects, including human life. According to the scientific research conducted, the only way to eliminate and prevent the problems that exist now and are likely to arise in the near future is the knowledge, skills, qualifications, acquired experience, educational process, as well as scientific research and science. It consists of effective coordination with the development of technology. This, in turn, directly puts new tasks before educational institutions in our country.

The training of advanced pedagogues and scientific personnel, ensuring their competitiveness in accordance with the requirements of the world labor market, training of independent and creative thinking specialists is closely related to the system based on which educational process is implemented in educational institutions [1].

Initial steps are being taken to abandon the negative aspects of the traditional education system and to organize work within the requirements of international standards.

Students studying in higher educational institutions will develop independent work skills and continue their work as teachers in general education schools as pedagogues in the future.

Since the credit-module system in higher education institutions is aimed at ensuring the professional development and maturity of students by ensuring independent work, it would be important to start this process, first of all, with the formation of independent learning skills of students in general secondary schools.

We know that each student's activity in the educational process is unique, and one does not repeat the other. Therefore, it is certainly inappropriate to evaluate their potential, talent, and behavior in the process of education in the same way, to see them in the same position. There is also a big difference in students' ability to do independent work in class and outside of class, thinking and potential. Organization of students' independent work, first of all, preparation for it is created by the teacher in such ways as problem-based presentation of materials.

Independent educational work means any active activity of students, such as searching for new knowledge, understanding, strengthening, forming and developing skills and competencies, generalizing and systematizing knowledge, organized by the teacher to fulfill the didactic goal set in a specially allocated time. As a didactic phenomenon, the independent work of students is, on the one hand, an educational task for him, because by performing it, the student must definitely achieve some result, on the other hand, due to the implementation of the relevant activity, the student's memory is strengthened while performing the educational task, and his free and creative thinking increases. as a result, it leads to a completely new knowledge of the student.

It is today's demand that English language teachers at school always organize independent work with students as much as possible. Therefore, it is necessary for the teachers to guide the independent work of the students in the English language classes and to provide them with continuous materials. It is rare to find a new approach to the organization of students' independent work in the subject of English in general secondary schools.

Among the subjects, the English language is distinguished by its own aspects of conversation, writing and listening. In order for the student to perform these aspects independently, knowledge, skills and creative abilities are required to be well developed. The reason for this is that students whose pronunciation, listening and writing skills are not well developed can somehow reduce their interest in science. It is important to increase students' passion for science by various methods in developing students' independent work skills in English classes, because where there is passion, there is quality education.

Carrying out exercises using information and communication technologies in English language classes for general education school students will greatly help to increase the creative activity of students and develop independent work skills.

The independent work system develops in students individuality, logical thinking, and the desire to learn in the future. Systematic assimilation of knowledge by students develops psychological attitude and skills of acting in the flow of scientific and mass information while solving new tasks. Independent work plays an important role in the formation and development of educational skills, increasing the will and cognitive interests. It shows the individuality of each student, their intelligence and character are formed. All this allows to acquire knowledge at a deep and powerful level [2].

In many cases, the same type of work allows you to solve several problems at the same time. For example, when students independently study new material, read a textbook or do exercises, along with understanding new knowledge, their existing knowledge is improved, the results are self-checked, and in some cases, this is usually done in the form of a test.

Today, the methods of independent work established in general secondary schools do not correspond to the credit module system currently established in higher education institutions. In most cases, students' independent learning concepts in general education schools are limited to the problems and exercises given in the textbook.

It is difficult to imagine the English language without information and communication technologies. Conducting lessons using computer programs in the educational process helps to achieve the following achievements: making the lesson more interesting and demonstrative; involve all students in the learning process; provides opportunities to use information in a short time, independent and distance education.

The main purpose of using information technologies in the teaching process is to achieve a new quality in education, to provide the educational process methodically with the help of modern, mainly interactive, educational tools and forms, as well as to increase the independent learning skills and creative activity of schoolchildren. it helps a lot.

References:

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